

COMPRESSIBILITY AND FINITE-RATE CHEMISTRY INFLUENCE ON REACTIVE SHEAR LAYERS DEVELOPMENT

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Abstract

The shear layers growth rate is known to be altered by compressibility and heat release effects. On the one hand, for increasing levels of compressibility, there is indeed a decrease in pressure fluctuations leading to a reduction in pressure-strain terms, which is responsible for the decrease in growth rate. On the other hand, previous numerical simulations showed that the main influence of the thermal expansion is to reduce the magnitude of the vorticity within the vortex cores and reaction zones, while the baroclinic torque generates alternate regions of positively and negatively signed vorticity at the braids and vicinity of vortex cores. The combination of the two effects favors the diffusion of the vorticity field as well as its attenuation within the vortex core, which results in lower growth rates of sheared layers. Such insights were mostly gained from the consideration of temporally developing mixing layer analyses that relate the longitudinal spatial coordinate to time *via* the introduction of an artificial average velocity across the layer. In this case, the flow becomes symmetric with respect to its development axis, and it does not distinguish between the fluids from the two streams with different velocities. The analysis of both compressibility and heat release is revisited here by considering numerical simulations of spatially-developing high speed reactive shear layers for different convective Mach number values including the influence of finite rate chemistry effects. The evolution of the vorticity thickness growth rate is analysed in detail in the light of the turbulent kinetic energy and enstrophy budgets. If the use of global single step chemistry tend to support previous findings, that were obtained from temporally developing mixing layer simulations, the conclusions presently drawn from the consideration of finite rate chemistry effects through the use of detailed chemical kinetics are different. Finally, these investigations are further extended to the consideration of shocked (reactive) mixing layers, a situation significantly less documented in the literature.

Introduction

Numerical simulations of high-speed reactive shear layers already concentrated a large amount of research efforts, see for instance [1, 2], and the interest in such reactive flow conditions has been, to a large extent, motivated by the development of airbreathing vehicles able to cruise at hypersonic speeds. Most of the aforementioned works dealt with temporally developing turbulent reactive mixing layers and often considered either single-step chemistry or infinitely fast chemistry. Numerical simulations of spatially-developing high speed mixing layers were much seldom reported in the literature and mainly devoted to inert situations [3, 4]. The amount of computer resources needed to obtain an equivalent resolution is indeed greater for spatially growing layers but they display some important differences with temporal simulations. In spatially-developing mixing layers, events that occur downstream can influence the flowfield upstream, whereas in temporally developing layers, no event can affect the flow at previous times. Moreover, in contrast with temporally developing layers, entrainment rates of fluid from the two streams are not necessarily the same. In the present work, direct numerical simulations of spatially-developing shear layers are performed for reactive conditions, and including a detailed description of molecular transport also. Figure 1, which reports a numerical Schlieren superimposed with temperature iso-lines at a convective Mach number value $M_c = 0.8$, pro-

vides a typical example of the results that may be obtained from the two-dimensional numerical simulation of a mixing layer developing between vitiated air and hydrogen mixture streams ¹.

Figure 1: Temperature iso-contours superimposed on numerical Schlieren of the pressure field.

Transport equations and numerical methods

The present numerical study is carried out with a multicomponent compressible and reactive flow solver. Special attention is paid to the competition that may exist between molecular diffusion and chemical kinetics as well as complex flowfield structures that may feature shock and expansion waves. We therefore consider the compressible Navier-Stokes equations written for a reactive multicomponent mixture characterized by the conservative vector $\mathbf{q} = (\rho, \rho u_1, \rho u_2, \rho u_3, \rho e_t, \rho Y_1, \dots, \rho Y_\alpha, \dots, \rho Y_{N_{sp}})^t$, where ρ denotes the density, u_i are the components of the velocity vector, p is the pressure, e_t is the total energy, Y_α is the mass fraction of the α th species ($\alpha = 1, \dots, N_{sp}$) with N_{sp} the total number of chemical species.

The corresponding system of conservative equations is supplemented with the ideal-gas equation of state $p = \rho \mathcal{R} T / \mathcal{W}$, with \mathcal{R} the universal gas constant and \mathcal{W} the molecular mass of the mixture obtained from $\mathcal{W}^{-1} = \sum_{\alpha=1}^{N_{sp}} Y_\alpha / \mathcal{W}_\alpha$. The specific heat capacities at constant pressure and enthalpies for each species are expressed as polynomial forms of the temperature involving a series of coefficients determined from the JANAF databases. The j -component of the heat flux is evaluated from $\mathcal{J}_j = \sum_{\alpha=1}^{N_{sp}} \rho Y_\alpha V_{\alpha,j} (h_\alpha + \mathcal{R} T \tilde{\chi}_\alpha / \mathcal{W}_\alpha) - \lambda \partial T / \partial x_j$, where λ is the thermal conductivity of the mixture and $\tilde{\chi}_\alpha$ is the rescaled thermal diffusion ratios of the α th species, which is defined in such manner that $D_{\alpha\beta} X_\beta \tilde{\chi}_\beta = \theta_\alpha$, with α and $\beta \in [1, \dots, N_{sp}]$. In the previous expression, θ_α and $D_{\alpha\beta}$ denote the thermal diffusion vector and diffusion matrix, respectively, while X_β denotes the β th species molar fraction. The j -component of the molecular diffusion flux is represented by $\rho Y_\alpha V_{\alpha,j} = - \sum_{\beta=1}^{N_{sp}} \rho \tilde{D}_{\alpha\beta} (d_{\beta,j} + (X_\beta \tilde{\chi}_\beta / T) \partial T / \partial x_j)$, with $d_{\beta,j} = \partial X_\beta / \partial x_j + (X_\beta - Y_\beta) \partial \ln P / \partial x_j$, where $\tilde{D}_{\alpha\beta}$ is the flux diffusion matrix formed by the flux diffusion components $Y_\alpha D_{\alpha\beta}$. All the transport coefficients mentioned above, i.e., $\tilde{D}_{\alpha\beta}$, $\tilde{\chi}_\beta$ as well as the volume and shear viscosity κ and μ are evaluated using the general purpose fortran library EGLIB [5].

The solver handles detailed chemical kinetics as described through N_r elementary reaction steps involving N_{sp} chemical species $\sum_{\alpha=1}^{N_{sp}} \nu'_{\alpha,j} \mathcal{M}_\alpha \rightleftharpoons \sum_{\alpha=1}^{N_{sp}} \nu''_{\alpha,j} \mathcal{M}_\alpha$, $j = 1, \dots, N_r$, where \mathcal{M}_α is the chemical symbol for the α th species, while $\nu'_{\alpha,j}$ and $\nu''_{\alpha,j}$ denote the stoichiometric coefficients. The resulting chemical source terms are given by $\dot{\omega}_\alpha = \sum_{j=1}^{N_r} (\nu''_{\alpha,j} - \nu'_{\alpha,j}) q_j$ with $q_j = k_{fj} \prod_{\alpha=1}^{N_{sp}} [X_\alpha]^{\nu'_{\alpha,j}} - k_{rj} \prod_{\alpha=1}^{N_{sp}} [X_\alpha]^{\nu''_{\alpha,j}}$, where k_{fj} and k_{rj} denote the forward and reverse rate constants of the j th elementary reaction, respectively, and $[X_\alpha]$ is the molar concentration of the α th species.

The treatment of the inviscid component of the transport equation for the conservative vector relies on the seventh-order accurate Weighted Essentially Non-Oscillatory (WENO7) recon-

¹Note that (eddy) shocklets are visible in Fig. 1, and their presence has been also evidenced in the three-dimensional numerical simulations we conducted under the same conditions.

struction of the characteristic fluxes [6]. In practice, the numerical solver uses a seventh-order accurate centered finite difference scheme, and the application of the WENO7 scheme is conditioned to a smoothness criterion which involves the local values of the normalized spatial variations of both pressure and density [7]. The viscous and molecular diffusion flux functions are determined using an eighth-order centered difference scheme. The temporal integration is performed using the Strang splitting technique: the non-reactive part of the equations is integrated in time thanks to an explicit third-order TVD Runge-Kutta algorithm [8] while the chemical production rates are calculated by solving a stiff system of Ordinary Differential Equations (ODEs) with the general purpose solver VODE [9]. Further details about the numerical methods as well as an exhaustive verification of the solver are provided in references [7, 10].

Table 1: Inlet stream conditions retained for inert and reactive numerical simulations.

	Global chemistry		Detailed chemistry	
	Fuel stream	Oxidizer stream	Fuel stream	Oxidizer stream
P (Pa)	94232.25	94232.25	94232.25	94232.25
T (K)	545.0	1475.0	545.0	1475.0
ρ (kg/m ³)	0.354	0.203	0.354	0.203
Y_{H_2} (-)	0.05	0.0	0.05	0.0
Y_{O_2} (-)	0.0	0.278	0.0	0.278
$Y_{\text{H}_2\text{O}}$ (-)	0.0	0.17	0.0	0.17
Y_{H} (-)	-	-	0.0	5.60×10^{-7}
Y_{O} (-)	-	-	0.0	1.55×10^{-4}
Y_{OH} (-)	-	-	0.0	1.83×10^{-3}
Y_{HO_2} (-)	-	-	0.0	5.10×10^{-6}
$Y_{\text{H}_2\text{O}_2}$ (-)	-	-	0.0	2.50×10^{-7}
Y_{N_2} (-)	0.95	0.552	0.95	0.55

Flow configuration and numerical setup

The parameters characterizing each inlet stream are determined from previous experimental and numerical studies, see for instance references [11, 12, 13] which are related to supersonic combustion ramjet (Scramjet) conditions. In these studies, hydrogen is the reference fuel because of its high level of energy per unit weight and shorter ignition delays. For instance, in the experimental study conducted by Miller *et al.* [11], the fuel stream is composed of hydrogen diluted with nitrogen (or helium) while the oxidizer stream corresponds to vitiated air obtained from combustion operated between hydrogen and air in a pre-chamber. The levels of heat release reached in this experiment were not large enough to induce significant changes in the large scale development of the reactive shear layer, which remains very similar to those previously reported for inert cases at the same level of compressibility. As the present study aims at investigating such heat release effects in high speed shear flows, the retained inlet flow conditions, presented in Table 1, slightly differ from those previously considered in [11]. We will denote by GC the simulations based on the global single step chemistry while DC will refer to simulations performed with a detailed chemistry representation. Conditions at chemical equilibrium are determined from a preliminary study in order to settle the radical mass fraction values in the vitiated air stream, see Table 1, the influence of which is far from being negligible [11].

From this preliminary study, we also determined the adiabatic temperature at equilibrium as well as the auto-ignition times. Figure 2(a) reports the temperature at equilibrium as a function of the mixture fraction z , i.e., a passive scalar defined to be unity in the fuel inlet stream and

zero in the oxidizer inlet stream. It is compared to the values associated with other inlet stream conditions that were previously considered in the literature: Miller *et al.* [11], Cheng *et al.* [12] and Sekar *et al.* [13]. The corresponding data can be used to obtain a rough estimate of the maximum levels of temperature that may be obtained within the shear layer and associated heat release. On the one hand, in the configuration of Miller *et al.* [11], the adiabatic temperature at equilibrium remains lower than the vitiated air stream temperature. On the other hand, in the configurations of Cheng *et al.* [12] and Sekar *et al.* [13], heat release is clearly more pronounced. Finally, our configuration appears as an intermediate case featuring a maximum temperature of 2400 K in the vicinity of the stoichiometry ($z_{st} = 0.41$) and, therefore, levels of heat release are expected to produce significant changes in the large scale development of the shear layer.

Figure 2: Adiabatic temperature level at equilibrium (a), and self-ignition time scale (b), for different values of the mixture fraction.

Figure 2(b) provides the self-ignition delays for the mixture considered in this work. Results associated with global chemistry (GC) have been obtained by using the single step global reaction of Marinov *et al.* [14] while those associated with detailed chemistry (DC) are based on the chemical reaction mechanism of O’Conaire *et al.* [15] featuring 21 elementary reactions steps and 10 species. As expected, the shortest ignition time values are obtained from the global reaction mechanism. However, the comparison of the results obtained with either a pure air or a vitiated air oxidizing stream confirms that the presence of chemical radicals significantly shortens the self-ignition delay, and also enlarges the flammable domain.

The inlet mixtures that have been considered above, see Table 1, will be used to specify the boundary conditions of spatially-developing numerical simulations of both inert and reactive mixing layers. The corresponding numerical simulations will be conducted for different levels of compressibility characterized by convective Mach number values $M_c = 0.35$, $M_c = 0.70$ and $M_c = 1.10$. In the case $M_c = 1.1$, two-dimensional numerical simulations did not lead to the destabilization of the shear layer. This confirms the conclusion of linear and nonlinear stability analyses, which indeed show that, as the convective Mach number increases, the most amplified modes are no longer two-dimensional and become three-dimensional with perturbations propagating with an angle θ relative to the (x_1, x_2) plane. This behavior has been also assessed for compressible reactive mixing layers [16]. In practice, despite the growth in computing performance, parametric DNS investigations with detailed transport and chemical kinetics description still remain limited by computational resources. The present study is therefore restricted to two-dimensional numerical simulations, which have already been shown to

accurately portray the characteristic large-scale rollup and vortex-pairing processes. Implications of chemistry-induced heat release on these processes are thus expected to be meaningfully addressed with such numerical simulations. The main conclusions obtained herein indeed concern the large-scale development of shear layers, i.e., under the principal influence of the large eddies resulting from the Kelvin-Helmholtz primary instability. Such characteristics are clearly less sensitive to three-dimensional small-scale dynamics. Finally, it is noteworthy that the insights gained from these two-dimensional numerical simulations have been confirmed from the results of two distinct three-dimensional numerical simulations of reference, which have been conducted for $M_c = 0.35$ under inert conditions, and $M_c = 0.70$ with detailed chemistry under reactive conditions.

In all cases to be investigated, the two inlet streams remain supersonic. The velocity in the oxidizer inlet stream is increased to reach the desired value of the convective Mach number, while the velocity in the fuel inlet stream is kept barely larger than the speed of sound. The initial vorticity thickness, $\delta_{\omega,0}$, is adjusted to maintain the same value of the initial Reynolds number $Re_{\omega,0} = 640$ for all the simulations. Numerical simulations are conducted in a computational domain with dimensions $L_1 \times L_2 = 350\delta_{\omega,0} \times 80\delta_{\omega,0}$ for $M_c = 0.35$ and $L_1 \times L_2 = 350\delta_{\omega,0} \times 122\delta_{\omega,0}$ for $M_c = 0.70$. These computational geometries are respectively discretized with $N_1 \times N_2 = 1739 \times 369$ points and $N_1 \times N_2 = 1739 \times 403$ points. Mesh stretching is applied in both directions of space. In the transverse direction, the grid size $\Delta x_2 = 0.168\delta_{\omega,0}$ is maintained constant from the center of the domain to $x_2 = \pm 20\delta_{\omega,0}$. A slight stretching is also applied along the longitudinal direction from the beginning of the computational domain, where $\Delta x_1 = 0.40\delta_{\omega,0}$, to $x_1 = 150\delta_{\omega,0}$ where a constant grid size $\Delta x_1 = 0.168\delta_{\omega,0}$ is set. In any case, the maximum grid size values conform with those retained in the direct numerical simulations conducted by Fu and Li [3] and the extent of the computational domain is sufficient to allow for the shear layer development [4]. Finally, the simulations are initialized with an hyperbolic tangent profile for the streamwise velocity component, temperature and species mass fractions [1]. A Dirichlet boundary condition is applied at the inlet while non-reflecting conditions are set at the outlet, bottom and top of the domain. A random perturbation is superimposed on the transverse velocity component within a gaussian spot centered at $(x_1, x_2) = (4\delta_{\omega,0}, 0)$ to trigger the destabilization of the mixing layer.

Spatially-developing shear layers analysis

Figure 3 shows the instantaneous structure of the inert and reactive shear layers for two convective Mach number values. The top inlet stream is associated with fuel injection and the bottom with oxidizer injection. The structure corresponding to the inert case at $M_c = 0.35$ (I-2D-0.35) shows a certain level of coherence with three (approximately) equidistant elliptical-shaped vortices in the domain $x_2/\delta_{\omega,0} \in [200, 350]$. As the convective Mach number value is increased, the flowfield structure becomes more distorted and the coherence evidenced in the previous case is no longer observed. For the reactive cases, two different flow structures can be observed depending on the retained reaction mechanism. With the detailed reaction mechanism of O’Conaire *et al.* [15], the flow field structure remains similar to the one of the inert cases. Heat release levels are present on the fuel lean side, delineating the high temperature regions. These regions are continuous at $M_c = 0.35$ (DC-2D-0.35) and become isolated spots at $M_c = 0.70$, suggesting that the influence of heat release is less important in this case. With the global reaction mechanism of Marinov *et al.* [14], the shear layer is more severely affected by heat released, whatever the level of compressibility. Low density fluid in the mixing region results in a shift of the unstable mode to lower wave numbers (longer wavelengths). Indeed, when single step chemistry is retained, the largest part of heat release occurs in the early development

of the shear layer, which explains why there are only few traces of heat subsequently released further downstream, where almost all hydrogen and oxygen have already been converted into combustion products.

Table 2 reports some quantitative confirmations of the qualitative observations discussed above. The vorticity thickness δ_ω is defined as

$$\delta_\omega = \frac{\Delta U}{|\partial \langle u_1 \rangle_f / \partial x_2|_{\max}}, \quad (1)$$

where $\Delta U = U_1 - U_2$. Operator $\langle \cdot \rangle$ refers to Reynolds average while the same operator with index f , i.e., $\langle \cdot \rangle_f$, denotes Favre average. Primes and double primes indicate the corresponding fluctuations. It can be seen that the vorticity thickness growth rate, given by $\eta^{-1} d\delta_\omega / dx_1$ with $\eta = (U_1 - U_2) / (U_1 + U_2)$, is greater in inert cases. Significantly lower values of the growth rate are obtained with global chemistry, which features the shortest ignition delays and also the largest heat release levels. With a detailed chemical kinetics description, the same tendency is observed at $M_c = 0.35$. However, the growth rate value reached at $M_c = 0.70$ is very close to the one previously found under inert conditions, see Table 2, which is confirmed by the flowfield structures displayed in Figs. 3(b) and 3(d). Heat release levels become indeed lower at higher levels of compressibility when using detailed kinetics, whereas the opposite trend is observed with global single-step chemistry. The results obtained here with detailed chemical kinetics contrast with those issued from several numerical simulations conducted in similar conditions under the fast chemistry assumption which did not evidence the same effects.

Figure 3: Fields of the normalized temperature $c = (T - T_{\min}) / (T_{\max} - T_{\min})$ superimposed with iso-lines of heat release for the inert and reactive spatially-developing shear layers.

Figure 4 provides the normalized growth rate values. Results obtained for inert conditions are found comparable with standard data available from the literature [16, 17, 18, 19]. Here, the reference growth rate δ'_i has been obtained from the preliminary simulation of an inert and incompressible air-air mixing layer, which is not presented here just for the sake of conciseness. The values of the Reynolds number, $Re_\omega = Re_{\omega,0}\delta_\omega/\delta_{\omega,0}$, reached at the location $x_1 = 300\delta_{\omega,0}$, where most of the data post-processing will be performed, are also comparable to those associated with previous numerical investigations conducted in similar conditions [1, 2, 20].

Table 2: Results obtained from inert and reactive spatially-developing shear layers. The Reynolds number is computed at $x_1 = 300\delta_{\omega,0}$.

Cas	$\eta^{-1}d\delta_\omega/dx_1$	Re_ω
I-2D-0.35	0.143	6421
I-2D-0.70	0.133	8247
DC-2D-0.35	0.103	5158
DC-2D-0.70	0.129	7884
GC-2D-0.35	0.049	3735
GC-2D-0.70	0.031	4638

Figure 4: Normalized growth rates vs. M_c .

Figure 5 illustrates the budget of the turbulent kinetic energy (TKE) for each simulation as a function of x_2/δ_ω . The TKE transport equation is given by

$$\begin{aligned} \frac{D\langle\rho\rangle k}{Dt} = & -\langle\rho\rangle \left(R_{lk} \frac{\partial\langle u_l\rangle_f}{\partial x_k} \right) - \langle\rho\rangle \left(\frac{1}{\langle\rho\rangle} \langle\tau'_{lk}\frac{\partial u_l''}{\partial x_k}\rangle \right) \\ & - \frac{1}{2} \frac{\partial}{\partial x_k} \langle\rho u_l'' u_l'' u_k'' + 2p' u_l' \delta_{lk} - 2\tau'_{lk} u_l''\rangle + \langle p' \frac{\partial u_k''}{\partial x_k} \rangle + \langle u_l'' \rangle \left(\frac{\partial\langle\tau_{lk}\rangle}{\partial x_k} - \frac{\partial\langle p\rangle}{\partial x_l} \right). \end{aligned} \quad (2)$$

The first contribution in the RHS of the above equation is the production term $\langle\rho\rangle P$. It is followed by the dissipation rate $\langle\rho\rangle\epsilon$, the transport term T , the pressure dilatation contribution Π , and the mass flux coupling term Σ [20]. As shown in Fig. 5, for the present set of two-dimensional numerical simulations of inert and reactive mixing layers, the most important contributions to the TKE budget are the production and transport terms, $\langle\rho\rangle P$ and T . Their levels get reduced as the convective Mach number M_c is increased or heat release is present, a behavior similar to the one observed for the vorticity thickness growth rate. This tendency is even more pronounced for the simulation conducted with global chemistry at $M_c = 0.70$.

The influence of compressibility and heat release on the shear layer growth rate is further investigated by studying the enstrophy transport equation

$$\frac{D\langle\omega_i\omega_i\rangle}{Dt} = 2\langle\omega_i\omega_j\frac{\partial u_i}{\partial x_j}\rangle - 2\langle\omega_i\omega_j\frac{\partial u_j}{\partial u_i}\rangle + 2\langle e_{ijk}\omega_i\frac{1}{\rho^2}\frac{\partial\rho}{\partial x_j}\frac{\partial p}{\partial x_k}\rangle + 2\langle e_{ijk}\omega_i\frac{\partial}{\partial x_j}\left(\frac{1}{\rho}\frac{\partial\tau_{km}}{\partial x_m}\right)\rangle. \quad (3)$$

The four terms appearing in the RHS of Eq.(3) describe, respectively, vortex stretching, volumetric expansion (or compression), baroclinic torque and viscous effects. The dilatation and baroclinic mechanisms are strictly zero in constant-density flows. Volumetric dilatation may

occur when the density decreases due to heat release and, since the term $\partial u_j / \partial x_j$ is positive for expanding flows, the quantity $-\omega_i \omega_j \partial u_j / \partial x_j$ is associated with a possible enstrophy reduction mechanism. Finally, the baroclinic torque represents the generation (or destruction) of vorticity induced by the differential fluid accelerations that result from non-aligned pressure gradients and density gradients.

Figure 5: TKE cross-stream budget evaluated at $x_1 = 300\delta_{\omega,0}$ for inert and reactive spatially-developing mixing layers. Quantities are made non dimensional with ΔU and δ_{ω} .

Figure 6 displays the last three terms of the RHS of Eq.(3) for $M_c = 0.35$ and $M_c = 0.70$. Whatever the level of compressibility, baroclinic torque, which contributes to the production of enstrophy, and viscous diffusion, which contributes to its destruction, are the most important terms in the enstrophy budget of inert and reactive mixing layers². The dilatation term plays a less important role in the destruction of enstrophy whereas the vortex stretching mechanism is not represented in such two-dimensional numerical simulations. At $M_c = 0.35$, the heat release decreases the amplitudes of dilatation, baroclinic torque and viscous diffusion terms. At $M_c = 0.70$, there is no clear reduction of these terms in the reactive case using detailed kinetics compared to the inert case. This also explains why the growth rates are very similar for this two configurations (I-2D-0.70 and DC-2D-0.70). Moreover, the levels of enstrophy production (baroclinic torque) when using detailed chemistry are higher when compressibility increases, see Figs. 6(b) and 6(e), thus enhancing the shear layer growth rate. Nevertheless, the use of a global reaction mechanism at $M_c = 0.70$ results in the lowest values of the production/destruction terms involved in the enstrophy budget. Finally, it is also worth noting that, in reactive cases at $M_c = 0.35$, these terms display an asymmetry for negative values of the transverse coordinate. The corresponding locations area is associated with the fuel lean side, where combustion occurs, see Figs. 3(c)–3(f).

²Note that this will not be necessarily the case for three-dimensional numerical simulations, where vortex stretching may compensate the viscous diffusion term.

Figure 6: Enstrophy budget for the inert and reactive naturally developing mixing layers, computed at $x_1 = 300\delta_{\omega,0}$. Quantities are made non dimensional with ΔU and δ_{ω} .

Shocked spatially-developing shear layers

The above results confirmed that mixing between fuel and air streams under highly compressible conditions is inherently slow. However, since shock waves (SW) are present inside the intake and combustor of Scramjet engines, shock wave impingement may provide an attractive method to enhance mixing. In this last section, we report numerical simulations of both inert and reactive shear layers interacting with steady oblique shock waves.

Figure 7: Sketch of the SW mixing layer interaction geometry. **0:** splitter plate; **1:** SW generator; **2:** incident SW; **3:** shear layer; **4** and **6:** reflected SW; **5:** transmitted SW.

Figure 7 provides a schematic view of the flow configuration. The fuel (top) and oxidizer (bottom) inlet stream properties remain strictly the same as those considered in the above cases and, therefore, values gathered in Table 1 still hold. The initial Reynolds number value is kept to 640 and the convective Mach number is set to $M_c = 0.48$. The computational domain size is $L_1 \times L_2 = 275\delta_{\omega,0} \times 120\delta_{\omega,0}$ and is uniformly discretized in space using $N_1 \times N_2 = 1638 \times 717$

grid points. A Dirichlet boundary condition is applied at the inlet of the computational domain while a slip boundary condition is imposed at the top and a non-reflecting boundary condition is set at the outflow. The bottom boundary condition is set by using Rankine-Hugoniot relations, generalized for a multicomponent mixture [21], and subject to an oblique shock wave featuring a SW angle $\beta = 33^\circ$, see Fig. 7. Finally, the flow initialization and perturbation procedures presented in the previous section are kept.

Figure 8: SW interaction with spatially-developing shear layers. Instantaneous temperature fields superimposed with numerical Schlieren (dark lines). Iso-lines of heat release. SI units.

Figure 9: Normalized TKE budget (a) and entrophy budget (b) computed at $x_1 = 250\delta_{\omega,0}$. Quantities are made non dimensional with ΔU and δ_{ω} .

Figure 8 displays instantaneous plots of the flowfield structures associated with the inert and reactive mixing layers as obtained from the consideration of the detailed mechanism of

O’Conaire *et al.* [15]. The two structures are quite similar. In the reactive simulation, the temperature field reflects the presence of isolated spots featuring higher temperatures after the first SW interaction, but chemical reaction becomes more significant after interaction with the reflected SW. An additional combustion-induced SW (labelled 6 in Fig. 7) appears as an outcome of the Mach number decrease due to local heat release, which makes the flow slightly subsonic at this location. In this region, the measured vorticity thickness growth rate is 0.221 and 0.205 for the inert and reactive cases, respectively. These are larger than those obtained from previous simulations, see Table 2, emphasizing the potential efficiency of SW impingement. Figure 9(a) reports the TKE budget for the inert and reactive cases. The maximum levels are the same order of magnitude as those obtained from the I-2D-0.35 simulation. Levels of baroclinic torque and viscous diffusion are reduced in the reactive case, as shown in Fig. 9(b).

Conclusions and future works

Numerical simulations of spatially-developing inert and reactive shear layers have been conducted with special emphasis placed on the combined effects of compressibility and finite-rate heat release. The analyses of shear layer growth rates have been consolidated by considering TKE and enstrophy budgets. The results based on single step chemistry tends to confirm that heat release reduces the mixing rate, a standard conclusion, which was often drawn from numerical investigations conducted under the fast chemistry assumption. However, inclusion of finite rate chemistry effects through the consideration of a detailed reaction scheme is found to alter significantly this statement, thus emphasizing the importance of accounting for detailed chemical kinetics to address such issues. Finally, our investigation is supplemented with additional numerical simulations that aim at quantifying the influence of shock-wave impingement on the shear layer growth rate. The analysis is now being completed with three-dimensional direct numerical simulations, the objective of which are to confirm the reported trends.

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References

- [1] C. Pantano, S. Sarkar, and F. A. Williams, “Mixing of a conserved scalar in a turbulent reacting shear layer,” *Journal of Fluid Mechanics*, vol. 481, pp. 291–328, 2003.
- [2] I. Mahle, H. Foysi, S. Sarkar, and R. Friedrich, “On the turbulence structure in inert and reacting compressible mixing layers,” *Journal of Fluid Mechanics*, vol. 593, pp. 171–180, 2007.
- [3] S. Fu and Q. Li, “Numerical simulation of compressible mixing layers,” *International Journal of Heat and Fluid Flow*, vol. 27, pp. 895–901, 2006.
- [4] S. Stanley and S. Sarkar, “Simulations of spatially developing two-dimensional shear layers and jets,” *Theoretical Computational Fluid Dynamics*, vol. 9, pp. 121–147, 1997.
- [5] A. Ern and V. Giovangigli, “Fast and accurate multicomponent transport property evaluation,” *Journal of Computational Physics*, vol. 120, pp. 105–116, 1995.
- [6] C.-W. Shu, *Essentially non-oscillatory and weighted essentially non-oscillatory schemes for hyperbolic conservation laws*. ICASE Report, 1997.

- [7] P. J. M. Ferrer, R. Buttay, G. Lehnasch, and A. Mura, "A detailed verification procedure for compressible reactive multicomponent Navier-Stokes solver," *under consideration for publication in Computers & Fluids*, 2013.
- [8] S. Gottlieb and C. W. Shu, "Total variation diminishing Runge-Kutta schemes," *Mathematics of Computation*, vol. 67, pp. 73–85, 1998.
- [9] P. N. Brown, G. D. Byrne, and A. C. Hindmarsh, "VODE: a variable coefficient ODE solver," *Journal on Scientific and Statistical Computing*, vol. 10, pp. 1038–1051, 1989.
- [10] P. J. M. Ferrer, G. Lehnasch, and A. Mura, "Direct numerical simulations of high speed reactive mixing layers," *Journal of Physics: Conference Series*, vol. 395, 2012.
- [11] M. F. Miller, C. T. Bowman, and M. G. Mungal, "An experimental investigation of the effects of compressibility on a turbulent reacting mixing layer," *Journal of Fluid Mechanics*, vol. 356, pp. 25–64, 1998.
- [12] T. S. Cheng, J. A. Wehrmeyer, and R. W. Pitz, "Raman measurement of mixing and finite-rate chemistry in a supersonic hydrogen-air diffusion flame," *Combustion and Flame*, vol. 99, pp. 157–173, 1994.
- [13] B. Sekar and H. S. Mukunda, "A computational study of direct simulation of high speed mixing layers without and with chemical heat release," *Symposium (International) on Combustion*, vol. 23, pp. 707–713, 1990.
- [14] N. M. Marinov, C. K. Westbrook, and W. J. Pitz, "Detailed and global chemical kinetics model for hydrogen," *8th International Symposium on Transport Properties*, 1995.
- [15] M. O’Conaire, H. J. Curran, J. M. Simmie, W. J. Pitz, and C. K. Westbrook, "A comprehensive modeling study of hydrogen oxidation," *International Journal of Chemical Kinetics*, vol. 36, pp. 603–622, 2004.
- [16] M. J. Day, W. C. Reynolds, and N. N. Mansour, "The structure of the compressible reacting mixing layer: insights from linear stability analysis," *Physics of Fluids*, vol. 10, pp. 993–1007, 1998.
- [17] P. E. Dimotakis, *Turbulent free shear layer mixing and combustion*, S. Murthy and E. Curran, Eds. High Speed Flight Propulsion Systems, Progress in Astronautics and Aeronautics, AIAA, pp. 265-340, 1991.
- [18] J. R. DeBisschop and J. P. Bonnet, *Mean and fluctuating velocity measurements in supersonic mixing layers*, W. Rodi and F. Martelli, Eds. Engineering Turbulence Modelling and Experiments 2, Elsevier, 1993.
- [19] J. L. Hall, P. E. Dimotakis, and H. Rosemann, "Experiments in nonreacting compressible shear layers," *AIAA Journal*, vol. 31, pp. 2247–2254, 1993.
- [20] C. Pantano and S. Sarkar, "A study of compressibility effects in the high-speed turbulent shear layer using direct simulation," *Journal of Fluid Mechanics*, vol. 451, pp. 329–371, 2002.
- [21] R. E. Mitchell and R. J. Kee, *A general-purpose computer code for predicting chemical kinetic behavior behind incident and reflected shocks*. Sandia National Laboratories, 1989.